

LEXICAL GRAMMATICAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN TRANSLATION

Umida Turdaliyeva

Graduate student of Namangan State University

EFL Teacher of Namangan District Specialized School

Abstract: This article provides detailed examples and information about translation transformations: lexical, grammatical and stylistic transformations. Translation transformations are analyzed in detail through the transformational model of translation.

Keywords: transformations of translation, transformational grammar, nuclear structure, stages of analysis, transformation and synthesis, transformational model of translation, situational-denotative model.

The transformational model of translation is based on N. Chomsky's rules of transformational grammar. Transformational grammar studies the rules of origin of syntactic structures characterized by the basic logical syntactic connection and similarity of lexemes. According to transformational grammar, all types of syntactic structures can be combined into nuclear structures in which the transparency of logical-syntactic structures is limited.

According to known transformation rules, surface structures are formed from nuclear structures. A.D. Schweitzer gives the following example, if we consider the English sentence John hit Bill as a nuclear structure, a number of transformations can be made from this sentence:

Bill was hit by John.

John's hitting Bill.

Bill's being hit by John.

The hitting of Bill by John.

It was John who hit Bill.

It was Bill who was hit by John

Let's consider another example. If we take the sentence "The child is reading" as a nuclear structure, the following artificial structures can be created based on the rules of transformational grammar: "The child is reading", "The child is reading", "The child is reading", in these structures the main relationship remains "the owner of the action is the action". V. N. Komissarov said that despite the diversity of the forms that make

up the structure, these transformations have a significant level of content and meaning in common.

We can observe that content relations are always clearly expressed in nuclear structures, unlike synthetic structures. The subject is always represented by a noun, the process by a verb, the subject by possessor, the object by a complement. In other words, the transformation of artificial structures into nuclear structures is a method of defining meaningful alternatives between grammatical and semantic categories.

The situational-denotative model of translation assumes that the content of all language signs appears in objects, events, relationships. Objects of real reality reflected in language signs are called denotation. The situation in real reality is the relationship between all the denotations. Therefore, the organizational parts of the speech embody a certain situation in reality.

After the translator has an idea about the situation described in the original text [a specific picture depicting a certain part of reality], he expresses this idea through other language tools.

Of course, the only purpose of the translation is to accurately describe the situation that is fully or for some reason incompletely described in the original text. In this situation, the translator makes one or another changes or additions to his translation with a proper understanding of the issue and thus achieves a complete and adequate translation.

Studying and analyzing the reality of the situation will clarify whether it is permissible or not to use a direct alternative option in the translation text. Here V.N. Let's dwell on an interesting example given by Komissarov. In the translation of the sentence "X was baited by the right" in English, the translator considered the direct alternative of the verb to bait - to torture, to torment, and give the translation of the sentence in the form of a sheep possible "X is suffering from a right-wing party". However, if the name of Roosevelt stands in the place of X, this alternative will have an inappropriate tone [in the opinion of V.N. Komissarov, the suffering of a person who has great popularity and was elected president of the country four times is inconceivable]. Having studied the reality, in this situation, the translator can offer a "softer" translation option - "the hard part is left to the information".

One of the advantages of the situational-denotative model of translation is the possibility that the translator can refer to real reality. However, this model does not fully explain why the translator refers to this reality. V.N. Komissarov believes that this

model of translation is limited in explaining the actions of the translator when the picture of the situation given in the original text is changed in order to help the full implementation of interlingual communication in the translated language, that is, the person to whom the translated text is intended belongs to another culture. because of this, he cannot draw the necessary conclusions from the picture of the situation. In addition, the situational-denotative model does not interpret not only the description of the situation in the translation, but also the method of describing the situation described in the original text and the content of the main part of the language tools used in the translation.

However, we cannot fully agree with this opinion of the scientist. It is understood that in practice the translator always refers to the real reality, that is, not understanding the essence of the described situation can end with a correct translation only in some cases. In the translation, the preservation of some language tools and the style of describing the situation does not recognize that the translation was made on the basis of a different model. A translator may feel that this passage can be rendered in the same way in both languages [My brother lives in Moskow], and in this case there is no need to look for other methods of translation.

Here I.I. Revzin and V.Y. Rosensweig's thoughts seem both interesting and dubious. According to them, the reproduction of information in one language through the means of another language, without direct reference to reality, is actually translation, and this situation is characteristic of all types of translation, and it is clearly visible in the activities of simultaneous translators. In the process of translating a text from one language to another, reference to reality is often felt in the translation of fiction. At this point, repeating the above point, it is worth noting that any translation process includes the stages of reception, analysis, understanding of the content of the original text. To understand the content of the original text is to perceive the real reality, the linguistic means behind it. A text whose fundamental essence is not understood cannot serve as an object of translation.

However, this model does not fully explain why the translator refers to this reality. V.N. Komissarov believes that this model of translation is limited in explaining the actions of the translator when the picture of the situation given in the original text is changed in order to help the full implementation of interlingual communication in the translated language, that is, the person to whom the translated text is intended belongs to another culture. because of this, he cannot draw the necessary conclusions

from the picture of the situation. In addition, the situational-denotative model does not interpret not only the description of the situation in the translation, but also the method of describing the situation described in the original text and the content of the main part of the language tools used in the translation.

The subject is always represented by a noun, the process by a verb, the subject by possessor, the object by a complement. In other words, the transformation of artificial structures into nuclear structures is a method of defining meaningful alternatives between grammatical and semantic categories. Of course, the only purpose of the translation is to accurately describe the situation that is fully or for some reason incompletely described in the original text. In this situation, the translator makes one or another changes or additions to his translation with a proper understanding of the issue and thus achieves a complete and adequate translation.

References:

1. Комиссаров. В. Н. Слово о переводе (Очерк лингвистического учения о переводе). - М.: Междунар. отношения, 1973. – 143с.
2. Комиссаров В. Н. Теория перевода (лингвистические аспекты). – М.: Высшая школа, 1990. – 253 с.
3. Сепир Э. Язык. Введение в изучение речи. – М.-Л.:ОГИЗ,1934.-223с.
4. Хомский Н. Прибыль на людях. - М.: Праксис, 2002. - 256 с.
5. Якобсон, Р. Избранные работы / Р. Якобсон. – М.: Прогресс, 1985. – 454 с.
6. Nishonqulov, S. (2022). KICHIK KOMPANIYADA AXBOROT TIZIMLARIDAN FOYDALANISH. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(1), 1-13.
7. Nishonqulov, S. F. O. G. L., & Solidjonov, D. Z. O. G. L. (2021). Ta'lim biznesida raqamli innovatsion texnologiyalar. *Science and Education*, 2(6), 233-238.
8. Bayram, E., & Auesbaevich, P. A. (2020). Methodology For Improving The Efficiency Of Competition Activities Based On Improving The Quality Of Explosive Forces Of Freestyle Wrestlers. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(3), 3621-3624.
9. Auesbaevich, P. A. (2020, August). IMPROVING THE PROCESS OF TRAINING FOR ACTIVITY ACCORDING TO THE CHARACTERISTICS OF KURASH. In *The 8 th International scientific and practical conference—Eurasian scientific congress* (August 9-11, 2020) Barca Academy Publishing, Barcelona, Spain. 2020. 370 p. (p. 178).

10. Seitova, Z. P. (2022). ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY AS AN IMPORTANT DIRECTION OF REFORMS IN MODERN UZBEKISTAN. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(12), 275-284.
11. Seitova, Z. P. (2022). Women of the Aral Sea Region: A New Approach, Problems and Their Solutions. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 5(4), 62-66.
12. Yoldashev, A. E. O., Nishonqulov, S. F. O., & Yoldasheva, M. R. Q. (2021). TA'LIMDAGI AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Scientific progress*, 2(3), 806-813.
13. Solidjonov, D., & Nishonqulov, S. (2021). TA'LIM BIZNESIDA YANGI INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNING QO'LLANISHI JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH VOLUME-1. *ISSUE-3 (Part-1, 18-JUNE)*, 1, 195-199.
14. NISHONQULOV, S. KICHIK BIZNESLAR UCHUN BLOKCHEYN TEXNOLOGIYASI. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 277-287.
15. Farxodjon ogli, N. S., & Odil ogli, R. B. (2021). Raqamli iqtisodiyot almashinuvining resurslar sarfiga sakkizta tasiri. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 1(1), 53-56.

